

How Agroforestry Can Enhance Organic Farms in Ireland

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Sheep grazing in the foreground, among *Quercus* (oak) and *Prunus avium* (cherry), with tree shelters

References

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The Irish farmed landscape can be enhanced by integrating trees, shrubs, and pasture, aligning organic and regenerative farming. Unlike conventional systems reliant on synthetic inputs, organic farms focus on planning and ecosystem resilience. By mimicking Ireland's natural woodland-pasture ecosystems, agroforestry can create balanced, self-sustaining environments that benefit livestock, biodiversity, and soil health.

Silvopasture fosters biodiversity while improving productivity. Deep-rooted trees enhance soil structure, improve drainage, and support beneficial fungi that mobilize nutrients. Soils prone to compaction and waterlogging benefit from tree cover, which regulates moisture and reduces runoff. Increased plant litter and organic matter further enrich soil fertility. Trees act as windbreaks, reducing erosion while providing shade and shelter that buffer temperature fluctuations. This is especially valuable in livestock systems, where heat stress can affect animal welfare and productivity.

Beyond farming benefits, agroforestry supports biodiversity. Tree canopies offer nesting sites for birds, while hedgerows and woodland edges serve as corridors for pollinators and pest-controlling predators. Trees intercept rainfall, reduce runoff, improve groundwater recharge and sequester carbon, aiding Ireland's climate goals.

The Organic Farming Scheme (OFS), Basic Payment Scheme (BPS), and agroforestry promote sustainable land use. OFS provides financial aid for biodiversity-friendly organic farming, while the Agroforestry Support Measure funds tree integration. BPS payments can still be claimed on agroforestry land if farming continues. Farmers can access multiple supports, improving soil health, biodiversity, and climate resilience while maintaining organic certification.

By restoring trees to the farmed landscape, Irish farmers can boost productivity while improving sustainability. Agroforestry blends traditional land management with modern ecological strategies, balancing food production with climate resilience.

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John Casey

Teagasc- the Agriculture
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